

CUBA - 2024

11TH TTP CONFERENCE

Cuba

<https://www.zooparaz.net/ttp11>

TTP.11

11th Tick & Tick-borne
Pathogen Conference

Cuba 2024

SCIENTIFIC PROGRAM ABSTRACT BOOK

TTP Conference is one of the most important conventions in the world devoted to taxonomy and evolution of ticks and tick – borne pathogens, their ecology and epidemiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis and strategies for their control including immunity and vaccines among others.

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1st - 6th

September, 2024

Havana, Varadero, Cuba

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Symposium Diagnosis and strategies for control of
ticks and tick-borne pathogens including immunity and vaccines
Room Guamá, Meliá Internacional Varadero

12:30-12:45

**Exploration of emerging tick-borne pathogens and neglected tick-borne diseases in Serbia:
Balkan model of One Health approach**

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Ticks (order Ixodida) are obligate blood-feeding ectoparasites of mammals, birds, and reptiles, which are globally important vectors of disease-causing agents that impact both human and animal health. Here we present the results of “One Health” approach implemented as interdisciplinary method to study the spread of tick borne pathogens (TBPs) between ticks, animals and humans, as well as integration of xenodiagnostic procedures in healthcare management of humans with tick infestation.

Throughout 4 consecutive years (2019-2022) we conducted a series of studies under “One Health” approach which included enrollment of patients and tick removed from them, as well as investigation of possible TBP foci within household of patients with emerging TBDs. Materials and datasets generated through this approach were analyzed via entomologic, microbiological and molecular analysis, including microfluidic real-time high-throughput PCR system that was used to test the DNA of the tick and human blood for the presence of 27 bacterial and eight parasitic TBPs.

From all ticks removed from humans *Ixodes ricinus* was the most frequent tick species. Different *Rickettsia* species were the most common TBPs identified in the ticks. We have detected and described cases of atypical infections caused by *R. helvetica* and *R. raoultii*, exposure to Tick-Borne Encephalitis virus as well as fatal imported case of Tick-Borne Encephalitis. In addition, we examined the platelet fraction from patient blood as a substrate for direct detection of TBPs causing bacteremia. One Health approach described in Serbia (Balkan model) is first implemented worldwide and will help to characterize the components of the chain of infection leading to human infection by TBPs as well as diagnostics of tick borne diseases caused by emerging pathogens.